

Exploring Burnout and Resilience among Family Medicine Physicians in PSMMC

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Abstract

Introduction: Physician burnout is strongly associated with adverse effects on patient care, physician health, workforce stability, and health costs. Resilience is understood as a protective factor, but its association with burnout within specific cultural and organizational contexts such as those in Saudi Arabia, remains inadequately studied. The main objective of this study was to assess the prevalence of burnout and resilience and examine their relationship among Family Medicine physicians at Prince Sultan Military Medical City (PSMMC).

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted among Family Medicine physicians at PSMC, who were selected via stratified sampling. Participants completed a structured questionnaire capturing demographic factors, the Oldenburg Burnout Inventory (16-items), and the Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (10-items). Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, Pearson's correlation coefficient, T-test, and one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA).

Results: A total of 296 family medicine physicians from PSMC participated. The majority of the respondents were female (74%) and Saudi nationals (97.3%). Most participants were aged 40 years or younger (81.8%), with nearly half (49.7%) having 6-10 years of clinical work experience. A substantial 40.6% of physicians reported clinically significant burnout (16.6% high, 24% medium), while 25.3% reported low levels of resilience. A significant moderate negative association was found between burnout and resilience ($r = -0.304$, $p < .01$). Additionally, the average resilience score was significantly higher among physicians with more clinical experience ($p = 0.004$) and those working in specialist clinics or urgent care compared to general clinics ($p = .006$).

Conclusion: Physician burnout is a prevalent and systemic issue among Family Medicine physicians at PSMC, affecting individuals uniformly regardless of their demographic characteristics. Physician resilience scores were negatively associated with burnout. Resilience scores differed significantly by work setting and years of clinical experience. Therefore, public health policy should address the impact of the workplace environment and organizational factors to effectively mitigate the crisis.

Keywords: Resilience, Burnout, workplace environment, organizational stressors, public health policy.

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Introduction

Physician burnout, characterized by emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and a reduced sense of personal accomplishment is a prevalent international issue. Studies of both physicians-in-training and practicing physicians consistently indicate that over half report burnout symptoms, which are strongly associated with adverse effects on patient care, physician health, workforce retention, and healthcare costs. This high prevalence and its far-reaching consequences position physician burnout as a critical public health crisis with detrimental implications for individuals, healthcare organizations, and the broader system [1]. The chronic psychological strain inherent in such

environments elevates the risk of professional burnout, which is defined by emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and diminished personal accomplishment [2].

The study indicated that physicians demonstrated higher resilience levels compared with the general working population in the US. An inverse relationship was found between resilience and burnout symptoms, suggesting that higher resilience is associated with lower burnout. However, significant burnout rates were still observed among the most resilient physicians, highlighting the need for additional solutions, such as addressing systemic issues in the clinical care environment, to effectively reduce burnout and enhance physician well-being [3].

In Saudi Arabia, the healthcare system is experiencing rapid changes as part of the Kingdom's Vision 2030, which imposes further demands on healthcare professionals to align with evolving national health goals [4]. Consequently, understanding the well-being of physicians, especially those in essential specialties such as Family Medicine, is crucial for the success of these reform initiatives.

Unlike the harmful effects of burnout, resilience the capacity to adapt positively to adversity, trauma, and significant stress has been identified as a vital protective factor [5]. For physicians, resilience allows them to manage the inherent challenges of clinical practice, sustain their passion for medicine, and deliver high-quality care without falling into chronic distress [6]. It is a modifiable trait that can be enhanced through targeted interventions, offering a potential strategy to reduce burnout [1].

Prince Sultan Military Medical City (PSMMC) is a major tertiary care center in Riyadh, the capital city of Saudi Arabia, serving a large patient population. The Family Medicine Department at PSMMC functions in diverse environments, such as outpatient clinics, primary care, and emergency or inpatient consultations. Each of these settings offers distinct work structures, patient acuities, and pressures, which may differentially affect physician well-being.

While the global literature establishes a general inverse relationship between burnout and resilience [1], the specific prevalence of these conditions and the nature of their relationship within the distinct cultural and organizational environment of a major Saudi medical city like PSMMC remain inadequately investigated. Therefore, this study aims to fill this gap by focusing specifically on Family Medicine Physicians at PSMMC. The primary aims of this research are to examine the relationships between burnout and resilience, and to assess the prevalence of burnout and resilience among these physicians.

Methods

Study Design, Setting, and Population

A cross-sectional study design was employed to assess the levels of burnout and resilience and to investigate the relationships between them among Family Medicine physicians at PSMMC. This study was conducted at the Prince Sultan Military Medical City (PSMMC) in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. The target population was all physicians formally employed in the Department of Family Medicine at PSMMC.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The inclusion criteria were any physician licensed in Family Medicine by the Saudi Commission for Health Specialties (SCFHS) and working at PSMMC, Riyadh. The Exclusion criteria were non-Family Medicine physicians, physicians not working at PSMMC, and physicians who refused to participate.

Sampling Methods and Sample Size

A stratified random sampling technique was used to ensure representation of different work settings within the Family Medicine Department, such as general clinics, specialty clinics, and urgent care. The sample size was determined using the formula for estimating a single population proportion [7]:

$$n = \left(Z_{\alpha/2} \right)^2 \frac{p(1-p)}{E^2} \quad (1)$$

Where:

$Z_{\alpha/2} = 1.96$ (the Z-value for a 95% confidence level)

$p = 0.25$ (expected proportion of burnout)

$E = 0.0493$ (approximately 0.05, the margin of error)

This calculation yielded a sample size of 296 participants.

Measures

The main outcome variable, burnout, was measured using the Oldenburg Burnout Inventory (OLBI), a 16-item survey that evaluates burnout through two dimensions: exhaustion (covering physical, cognitive, and affective aspects) and disengagement (reflecting negative attitudes toward work). Each dimension is represented by 8 items, with a mix of positively and negatively worded questions for psychometric balance. Responses are on a 4-point Likert scale, with reverse scoring for positively worded questions. Total scores range from 16 to 64, with higher scores indicating greater burnout [8].

The main predictor variable, resilience, was measured using the Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-RISC-10). Participants rated their feelings over the past month on a 5-point Likert scale (0 = Not true at all to 4 = True nearly all the time), with total scores ranging from 0 to 40. Higher scores indicate greater resilience [9]. Data were collected via a structured, self-administered questionnaire distributed through a Google Form link. Participants also provided demographic information, including gender, nationality, marital status, monthly income, number of family members, work setting, and years of clinical experience.

Statistical Analysis

Data analysis was conducted in IBM SPSS Statistics (Version 27). Descriptive statistics were presented as frequencies and percentages. The relationships between burnout and resilience were examined using Pearson's correlation coefficient. Furthermore, to examine the difference in burnout and resilience scores across sociodemographic and work setting variables, independent t-tests were used for comparisons between two groups, and one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used for comparisons involving more than two groups.

Ethical Considerations

This study was conducted in accordance with ethical standards, and informed consent was obtained from all participants. Participants' data were held securely and accessed only by authorized personnel. The information gathered was used exclusively for the purposes of this research analysis.

Results

The sociodemographic and work-related characteristics of the respondents are presented in Table 1. A total of 296 Family Medicine physicians from PSMMC participated. The majority of the respondents were female (74%) and Saudi nationals (97.3%). Most participants were aged 40 years or younger (81.8%), with nearly half (49.7%) having 6-10 years of clinical work experience. Physicians were primarily distributed between specialty clinics (48.3%) and general clinics (39.2%). Most participants were married with children (64.9%) and earned a monthly income between 10,000 and 20,000 SAR (63.2%).

Table 1: Sociodemographic Characteristics of Participants (n = 296).

Variables	Levels	n (Frequency)	% (Percent)
Gender	Male	77	26.00
	Female	219	74.00
Nationality	Non-Saudi	8	2.70
	Saudi	288	97.30
Age group	20-30	119	40.20
	31-40	123	41.60
	>40	54	18.20

Marital Status	Single	84	28.40
	Married with children	192	64.90
	Divorced / Widowed	20	6.80
Work settings	General clinic	116	39.20
	Speciality clinic	143	48.30
	Urgent care	37	12.50
Years of Clinical Experience	≤ 5 years	75	25.30
	6-10 years	147	49.70
	> 10 years	74	25.00
Monthly Income	< 10k	58	19.60
	10-20k	187	63.20
	> 20k	51	17.20
Number of family Individuals	1	24	8.10
	2	46	15.50
	3	96	32.40
	4	68	23.00
	≥5	62	20.90

The levels of burnout (OLBI) and resilience (CD-RISC-10), and their association, are presented in Table 2. The average burnout score was 40.92 (SD = 3.93), and the average resilience score was 26.85 (SD = 3.73). Pearson's correlation coefficient revealed a statistically

significant, moderate negative relationship between burnout and resilience among Family Medicine physicians, $r(294) = -0.304, p < .01$. This indicates that as levels of resilience among physicians decrease, levels of burnout tend to increase.

Table 2: The Levels of Burnout and Resilience and Their Interrelationship among Family Medicine Physicians at PSMMC (n =296).

Variable	M	SD	Total Burnout	Total Resilience
Total Burnout	40.92	3.93	-	-0.304**
Total Resilience	26.85	3.73	-0.304**	-

Notes: M = Mean; SD = Standard Deviation; ** significant at $p < 0.01$ (2-tailed)

The prevalence of burnout and resilience among the 296 Family Medicine physicians is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Prevalence of Burnout and Resilience among Family Medicine Physicians at PSMMC (n = 296)

Variable	Categories	n (%)
Total Burnout (OLBI)	Low	176(59.5%)
	Medium	71(24.0%)
	High	49 (16.6%)
Total Resilience (CD-RISC10)	Low	75 (25.3%)
	Medium	169 (57.1%)
	High	52 (17.6%)

Notes: n (%): frequency (percentage)

The results indicate that the majority of physicians (59.5%, n = 176) reported low levels of burnout, while 40.6% experienced clinically significant burnout, ranging from medium (24%, n = 71) to high (16.5%, n = 49) levels of burnout. Regarding resilience, one in four physicians (25.3%, n = 75) reported low resilience, while the rest fell into medium (57.1%, n = 169) or high (17.6%, n = 52) resilience categories.

Total Burnout scores (OLBI) were categorized based on the NovoPsych classification into low (0–49th percentiles), medium (55–88th percentiles), and high (≥ 88 th percentile). For resilience (CD-RISC-10), scores were categorized based on the 25th, 50th, and 75th percentiles, due to the absence of universally applicable cut-offs, into low (≤ 25), medium (25.01–29), and high (≥ 29.01) respectively.

Factors associated with burnout and resilience among Family Medicine physicians at PSMMC are presented in Table 4. The results show that none of the sociodemographic or occupational factors were significantly associated with burnout levels among Family Medicine physicians at PSMMC. Specifically, burnout scores were consistent across gender, nationality, age group, marital status, work setting, years of clinical experience, monthly income, and number of family members, with all $p > 0.05$.

In contrast, resilience levels among Family Medicine physicians at PSMMC were significantly influenced by work setting and years of clinical experience. A one-way ANOVA showed that physicians in specialty clinics (M = 27.36, SD = 2.67) and urgent care (M= 27.54, SD = 4.45) reported significantly higher resilience than those in general clinics (M =26.0, SD = 4.68), $p = .006$. Furthermore, resilience scores differed significantly by years of clinical experience, with more experienced physicians exhibiting higher resilience scores, $p = .004$. Finally, no other factors including gender, nationality, age, marital status, monthly income, and the number of family members were significant predictors.

Table 4: Factors Associated with Burnout and Resilience among Family Medicine physicians at PSMMC (n =296).

Variable	levels	Total Burnout		Total Resilience	
		Mean (SD)	P-value	Mean (SD)	P-value
Gender†	Male	40.69(5.15)	0.550	27.01(4.16)	0.659
	Female	41.00(3.40)		26.79(3.57)	

Nationality[†]	Non-Saudi	40.38(2.97)	0.692	25.12(4.08)	0.184
	Saudi	40.93(3.95)		26.89(3.71)	
Age group	20-30	41.15(4.59)	0.322	26.49(4.49)	0.292
	31-40	41.01(3.23)		27.24(2.83)	
	>40	40.92(3.77)		26.78(3.63)	
Marital status	Single	41.10(4.65)	0.815	26.17(4.94)	0.124
	Married with children	40.89(3.67)		27.16(3.19)	
	Divorced / Widowed	40.50(3.00)		26.75(2.00)	
Work setting	General clinic	41.04(5.00)	0.874	26.00(4.68)	0.006
	Speciality clinic	40.88(2.76)		27.36(2.67)	
	Urgent care	40.68(4.04)		27.54(4.45)	
Years of clinical experience	≤ 5 years	41.21(6.04)	0.192	25.63(5.71)	0.004
	6-10 years	41.13(2.65)		27.18(2.41)	
	> 10 years	40.92(3.24)		27.43(3.05)	
Monthly Income	< 10k	41.50(3.05)	0.447	27.07(2.69)	0.677
	10-20k	40.80(3.54)		26.71(3.81)	
	> 20k	40.69(5.77)		27.14(4.42)	
Number of family individuals	1	38.83(4.06)	0.076	27.63(3.90)	0.205
	2	41.20(3.92)		26.67(3.23)	
	3	41.00(2.89)		27.32(2.45)	
	4	40.82(3.00)		26.81(3.43)	
	≥5	41.50(5.65)		26.00(5.49)	

Notes: † for gender, nationality t-test was conducted; For other variables all p-values calculated from ANOVA.

Discussion

This study assessed levels of burnout and resilience, and their associations, among Family Medicine physicians at PSMC in Saudi Arabia. The key findings indicate that around two-in-five physicians reported clinically significant burnout levels. These findings suggest that burnout represents a workplace health issue. Furthermore, three-in-four physicians reported high levels of resilience, highlighting the importance of maintaining these levels to help protect physicians against burnout. The results also confirmed a moderate negative association between burnout and resilience, which aligns with global literature that positions resilience as a protective factor [5,6].

Furthermore, the results show that none of the sociodemographic or work-setting factors were associated with physician burnout levels. This indicates that the causes of burnout at PSMC are systemic and impact physicians uniformly across different demographic groups. In contrast, resilience was influenced by work setting and years of clinical experience. This contrast highlights that although personal resources such as resilience can provide some defense, they are insufficient to counteract the broader systemic drivers of burnout. These findings support the consensus that individual level interventions must be coupled with fundamental organizational changes [1,10].

Limitations

This study has several limitations. First, the cross-sectional study design restricts the ability to infer causality. Additionally, the data were self-reported and collected from a single institution, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. Furthermore, specific organizational level factors known to contribute to physicians' burnout and resilience were not measured.

Conclusions

In summary, approximately two-in-five physicians experience clinically significant burnout, and one-in-four demonstrate low resilience among Family Medicine physicians at PSMC. Burnout poses a universal risk that affects physicians across all demographic groups, whereas resilience varies more widely. Therefore, institutional strategies should extend beyond strengthening individual resilience and must focus on identifying and mitigating systemic organizational stressors within the

work environment to effectively protect physician well-being and maintain the quality of patient care.

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